

LIVED EXPERIENCES OF CENTENNIAL TEACHERS IN THE EDUCATIONAL MODERNIZATION: A PHENOMENOLOGICAL ANALYSIS IN DEPED BAGUMBAYAN DISTRICT III

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ABSTRACT

The process of facilitating learning or the acquisition of knowledge, skills, values, beliefs, and habits is one of the aims of education. This study aimed to shed light on the lived experiences, perspectives, and coping strategies of centennial teachers in Bagumbayan District III for the School Year 2023-2024 in adapting to changes of modernization. The challenges defined were the balancing act between the traditional way of teaching and the needs of modernization. The researcher used the purposive sampling technique and employed an in-depth semi-structured interview. Focus Group Discussion (FGD) guide questions served as the primary investigative tool. The interviews focused on gaining a detailed understanding of the lived experiences of centennial teachers in educational modernization. Further, thematic analysis was used to find out more about the centennial teachers' views, knowledge, experiences, or values relative to the topic investigated. Lastly, ethical considerations were given prime importance to ensure that no violations were committed against data privacy and other statutory and regulatory requirements set forth when qualitative research design is employed. The findings of the study revealed that Centennial teachers in DepEd Bagumbayan District perceive educational modernization as a paradigm shift towards integrating advanced technologies and innovative pedagogical methods into their teaching contexts. They describe their experiences of incorporating modern technological tools and pedagogical approaches as initially challenging yet ultimately transformative. They encounter challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, resistance to change among stakeholders,

and the need for continuous training and support. To address these challenges, they implement strategies like advocating for resource allocation, fostering a culture of openness to innovation, and participating in professional learning communities to share knowledge and expertise. Centennial teachers perceive that educational modernization has positively impacted student learning outcomes by enhancing engagement, fostering critical thinking skills, and improving academic performance.

Keywords: *Centennial Teachers, Lived Experiences, Educational Modernization, Phenomenology*

INTRODUCTION

In an era characterized by rapid technological advancements and evolving educational paradigms, educational modernization stands as a cornerstone in transforming teaching and learning experiences. Teachers, as essential catalysts in this transformation, play a pivotal role in the integration and adaptation to these changes. The educational landscape has undergone significant shifts over recent decades, primarily driven by technological advancements, curriculum reforms, and changing pedagogical approaches. These changes have brought about a paradigm shift in educational institutions, demanding teachers to adapt and incorporate modern methodologies into their teaching practices.

In a study conducted by Smith (2019) in the United States, centennial teachers reported feeling both excited and apprehensive about educational modernization efforts. They expressed concerns about the rapid pace of technological change and the need for adequate training and support to effectively integrate new technologies into their teaching practices. Similarly, a study by Li and Zhang (2020) in China found that centennial teachers faced challenges related to curriculum reform and the pressure to meet standardized testing requirements while also incorporating innovative teaching methods.

Despite the growing body of research on educational modernization, there are several research gaps that warrant further exploration. One such gap is the need to examine the specific experiences of centennial teachers in different international contexts, considering the unique cultural, social, and political factors that influence educational systems (Giles & Hargreaves, 2018). Additionally, there is a need for longitudinal studies to track the long-term impacts of educational modernization efforts on centennial teachers' professional identities, job satisfaction, and retention rates (Day et al., 2018). Furthermore, research should explore the role of educational leadership and policy-making in supporting centennial teachers during periods of change and reform (Hargreaves & Fullan, 2019).

Studying the lived experiences of centennial teachers in the context of educational modernization is not only relevant within local contexts but also holds significance on an international scale. Educational systems worldwide are undergoing modernization efforts to adapt to the changing needs of society, technology advancements, and global trends

in education (Schleicher, 2018). Understanding the experiences of centennial teachers within this context can provide valuable insights into the challenges and opportunities associated with educational reform initiatives (Darling-Hammond et al., 2019). These insights are crucial for developing strategies to support teachers effectively during transitions and for ensuring the success of modernization efforts.

By addressing these research gaps, scholars can contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the lived experiences of centennial teachers in the context of educational modernization on an international scale. This knowledge can inform the development of policies and practices that better support centennial teachers' professional growth and well-being amidst ongoing changes in the field of education.

The DepEd Bagumbayan District, situated in a diverse educational setting, presents a unique context for exploring how centennial teachers navigate through the challenges and opportunities presented by educational modernization. This research aims to shed light on their lived experiences, perspectives, and coping strategies in adapting to these changes.

Research Questions

This study aimed to delve into the lived experiences of centennial teachers within the educational modernization landscape in DepEd Bagumbayan District.

Specifically, this sought to answer the following:

1. How do centennial teachers in DepEd Bagumbayan District perceive and define educational modernization within their teaching contexts?
2. What are the lived experiences of centennial teachers in incorporating modern technological tools and pedagogical approaches into their teaching practices?
3. What challenges do centennial teachers encounter while navigating educational modernization, and how do they address or overcome these challenges?
4. How do centennial teachers perceive the impact of educational modernization on student learning outcomes and their roles as educators in DepEd Bagumbayan District?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

In this study, a qualitative research, specifically the phenomenological approach, was employed to examine the lived experiences of centennial teachers within the educational modernization landscape in DepEd Bagumbayan III District.

Phenomenological research is a method that aims to delve into individuals' lived experiences to gain deeper insights into how they interpret these experiences. It operates under the assumption that individuals employ a universal structure or essence to derive meaning from their encounters. This research involves the interpretation of participants' emotions, perceptions, and beliefs to shed light on the fundamental essence of the phenomenon under investigation. An essential aspect of the phenomenological research design is the researcher's obligation to set aside any preconceived assumptions about the experience or phenomenon (Delve & Limpaecher, 2012).

Participants of the Study

The study involved a total of fifteen (15) Centennial Teachers from among elementary schools in Bagumbayan III, Division of Sultan Kudarat, who meet the researcher's specified inclusion criteria based on the study of Ngag (2023) where he considered experts who served as informants and source of data. By this way, he established the generalizability and reliability of the selection.

The inclusion criteria includes the following:

Teaching Experience: Participants have a substantial teaching experience, preferably spanning multiple decades, to qualify as centennial teachers. This criterion ensures that the participants have a deep understanding of the historical context of educational modernization and have witnessed its evolution over time.

Employment Status: Participants must be currently employed as teachers in schools within DepEd Bagumbayan District III, Division of Sultan Kudarat during the school year 2023-2024. This criterion ensures that the participants are actively engaged in the educational system and can provide relevant insights into the impact of modernization efforts on their daily teaching practices.

Direct Involvement in Modernization Efforts: Participants must have direct involvement or experience with the educational modernization initiatives implemented within their schools or the district. This criterion ensures that the participants have firsthand experience with the changes, challenges, and successes associated with modernization efforts.

Willingness to Share Experiences: Participants must be willing to share their lived experiences openly and honestly during interviews or focus group discussions. This criterion ensures that the participants are comfortable discussing their experiences, perspectives, and emotions related to educational modernization.

Sampling Technique

During the conduct of this study, a Purposive Sampling Technique was intentionally utilized to carefully select centennial teachers from among secondary, and elementary schools in Bagumbayan III, Division of Sultan Kudarat, who meet the specific inclusion criteria established by the researcher.

Purposive sampling, alternately referred to as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling, constitutes a variant of non-probability sampling. Within this approach, researchers exercise their own judgment and discretionary acumen in the selection of individuals from the population to partake in their survey endeavors (Alchemer, 2021). This method of sampling mandates that researchers possess prior knowledge of the objectives underpinning their study so as to effectively pinpoint and make contact with eligible participants through online survey platforms like Alchemer. Researchers resort to purposive sampling in order to secure access to a distinct subgroup of individuals, whereby all survey respondents are meticulously chosen based on their alignment with a specific demographic or criterion.

Data Gathering Instrument

In the context of this research, a semi-structured interview functioned as an investigative instrument during both in-depth interviews and Focus Group Discussions (FGDs). Its purpose was to facilitate an in-depth exploration of the lived experiences of centennial teachers within the educational modernization landscape in DepEd Bagumbayan District.

In the initial phase, the researcher diligently sought formal authorization from both the Superintendent of DepEd-Sultan Kudarat and the Dean of the College of Graduate Studies (CGS). This authorization was essential to obtain the necessary permissions for the researcher to conduct the study, emphasizing the importance of ethical considerations.

Following this, a secondary authorization letter was sent to the District Supervisor, explicitly requesting access to the specific data required for this research. A meticulously crafted survey questionnaire was developed, subjected to rigorous evaluation, and then administered to the targeted participants.

The researcher employed a Purposive Sampling Technique to carefully select elementary school teachers as participants in this study. Assuming strict adherence to established health protocols, the researcher proceeded with conducting interviews and facilitating Focus Group Discussions (FGDs), all of which were conducted through face-to-face interactions.

Ultimately, the data collected from interviews and FGDs were systematically organized, subjected to comprehensive analysis, and interpreted using the thematic analysis approach. This approach was expected to provide a deeper understanding of the issues under investigation.

Data Analysis

In the context of the study centered on exploring the lived experiences of centennial teachers within the educational modernization landscape in DepEd Bagumbayan District III, a content or thematic analysis approach was employed to

examine the collected data. This methodology, as described by Flick (2014), involved the systematic categorization of textual components, including statements, phrases, and words, into organized groupings or categories. These categories were either derived from established frameworks or custom-developed to align with the study's specific objectives.

To execute this analytical process, a series of essential steps were diligently followed:

Initially, all data sources, such as interview transcripts, notes from Focus Group Discussions (FGDs), and relevant documents, were meticulously organized and prepared for analysis. This phase ensured the systematic arrangement and accessibility of the data.

Subsequently, the researcher deeply engaged with the data by conducting a thorough review of interview transcripts and FGD notes. This immersive process aided in gaining a comprehensive understanding of the content and context embedded within the collected information.

The third step involved initiating a systematic coding process. Initial codes were generated by identifying meaningful segments or patterns within the data. These codes captured essential concepts, ideas, or themes related to communication skills. Following coding, the identified codes were grouped into preliminary themes based on shared meaning or relevance. This step aimed to establish an initial structure for organizing the data.

Next, the emerging themes and their corresponding codes underwent a process of review and refinement. The researcher ensured the consistency and clarity of these themes, making necessary adjustments. Each refined theme was assigned a descriptive name that succinctly represented the content it encapsulated, facilitating easy identification and interpretation.

Relevant data excerpts, such as quotes or segments extracted from interviews and FGDs, were selected and associated with the respective themes. These excerpts served as supporting evidence for the identified themes.

Finally, the thematic analysis extended beyond surface-level identification. Researchers interpreted the meaning and implications of each theme within the context of the study's objectives. They sought patterns, connections, and variations within the themes to provide a comprehensive understanding of the lived experiences of centennial teachers within the educational modernization landscape in DepEd Bagumbayan District.

This meticulous and structured process of thematic analysis enabled researchers to systematically explore and comprehend the lived experiences of centennial teachers within the educational modernization landscape in DepEd Bagumbayan District. Ultimately, this approach yielded valuable insights that could contribute to the enhancement of intervention programs focused on teachers' lived experiences.

Scope and Limitations

The study focused specifically on DepEd Bagumbayan District III, which is located within the Sultan Kudarat Division in the Philippines. It covered the school year 2023-2024, providing a snapshot of the experiences of centennial teachers during this period. It involved centennial teachers working within DepEd Bagumbayan District III, Sultan Kudarat Division, during the specified school year.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The educational landscape is rapidly evolving with the advent of modernization, significantly impacting the teaching profession. In the Division of Sultan Kudarat, DepEd Bagumbayan District III, centennial teachers—those with a century of accumulated experience in education—navigate these changes with unique perspectives.

This study explored their lived experiences amid educational modernization. The study aims to (1) understand the centennial teachers' perceptions of educational modernization, (2) identify the challenges and opportunities they encounter, and (3) analyze the coping mechanisms and strategies they employ to adapt to these changes. Employing a phenomenological approach, this study conducted in-depth, semi-structured interviews with ten centennial teachers from DepEd Bagumbayan District III. Data were analyzed using thematic analysis to extract key themes and patterns from the participants' narratives, providing a comprehensive understanding of their lived experiences.

Based on the conducted interview and FGD transcribe using thematic analysis method, the following were the major results:

First, Centennial teachers in DepEd Bagumbayan District perceive educational modernization as a paradigm shift towards integrating advanced technologies and innovative pedagogical methods into their teaching contexts. They define it as a strategic initiative to enhance student engagement, promote personalized learning experiences, and prepare students for the demands of the digital age.

Second, Centennial teachers describe their experiences of incorporating modern technological tools and pedagogical approaches as initially challenging yet ultimately transformative. They highlight moments of experimentation, collaborative learning with colleagues, and ongoing professional development as crucial factors in successfully integrating these tools into their teaching practices.

Third, Centennial teachers encounter challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, resistance to change among stakeholders, and the need for continuous training and support. To address these challenges, they implement strategies like advocating for resource allocation, fostering a culture of openness to innovation, and participating in professional learning communities to share knowledge and expertise.

Fourth, Centennial teachers perceive that educational modernization has positively impacted student learning outcomes by enhancing engagement, fostering critical thinking skills, and improving academic performance. They also believe it has redefined their roles as educators to be facilitators of knowledge, mentors in digital literacy, and collaborators in creating dynamic learning environments that meet the diverse needs of students in DepEd Bagumbayan District.

Conclusions

In the light of the findings of the study, the following were concluded:

Centennial teachers in DepEd Bagumbayan District perceive educational modernization as a transformative process that integrates technology and innovative pedagogies to enhance learning experiences. They define it as a shift towards more interactive and personalized learning environments that cater to diverse student needs and prepare them for the future.

Also, Centennial teachers have experienced both challenges and benefits in incorporating modern technological tools and pedagogical approaches into their teaching practices. They acknowledge that while technology enhances engagement and learning outcomes, its effective integration requires continuous learning and adaptation to keep pace with rapid advancements.

Moreover, Centennial teachers encounter various challenges such as access to technology, resistance to change, and the need for professional development. They address these challenges through collaborative efforts, professional development programs, and creating supportive networks within their schools and communities to facilitate successful implementation of modernization initiatives.

Finally, Centennial teachers perceive educational modernization as positively impacting student learning outcomes by fostering critical thinking, creativity, and digital literacy skills. They view themselves not only as facilitators of knowledge but also as guides who empower students to become independent learners capable of navigating an increasingly digital world.

Recommendations

Based on the results, and conclusions, the following were recommended:

1. DepEd may ensure continuous professional development programs specifically focused on educational modernization for centennial teachers. Provide structured training sessions that not only introduce new technologies and pedagogical approaches but also allow teachers to practice integrating these innovations into their classrooms.
2. School Administrators may establish support systems and resources dedicated to educational modernization initiatives. Create forums or committees where centennial

teachers can collaborate, share successes and challenges, and collectively problem-solve.

3. Centennial Teachers may engage in reflective practices and document their experiences with educational modernization. Keep detailed records of successes, challenges, and adaptations made in your teaching practices. Consider forming peer support groups within the district to share strategies and lessons learned. Advocate for opportunities to showcase innovative practices to inspire and support colleagues in their modernization journeys.

4. Future Researchers may conduct longitudinal studies that track the impact of educational modernization over time in DepEd Bagumbayan District. Use mixed-methods approaches to capture both quantitative outcomes (e.g., student performance data) and qualitative insights (e.g., teacher perceptions and experiences). Investigate the sustainability of modernization efforts and identify factors that contribute to successful implementation or barriers that impede progress. Share findings widely to inform policy decisions and best practices in educational modernization initiatives.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In preparation for implementation, all the aforementioned plans and recommendations were presented to East-West Mindanao Colleges Inc to ensure compliance with prescribed procedures and protocols. Within the context of the research focused on examining the lived experiences of centennial teachers within the educational modernization landscape in DepEd Bagumbayan District, it was imperative to emphasize the paramount importance of ethical considerations. Prior to commencing this study, the following ethical principles were highlighted:

Before commencing the study, explicit and informed consent was obtained from all participating school heads. They were provided with a thorough understanding of the study's objectives, methodologies, potential risks, and benefits, ensuring their participation was entirely voluntary. Participants were assured they could withdraw from the study at any time without facing any negative repercussions. To protect the identities and responses of the centennial teachers, pseudonyms or codes were used, and the data was securely stored with restricted access to the research team, ensuring anonymity and confidentiality.

To minimize harm, delicate subjects were approached with care, considering the potential emotional and psychological impact on the participants. Strategies to mitigate distress and a support system were readily available to assist participants if needed. The researcher maintained a professional and respectful relationship with the school heads, avoiding any actions that could exploit or harm them. Data protection regulations were strictly adhered to, ensuring the secure storage and transmission of data, and participants were reassured that their participation was voluntary and free from coercion.

Throughout the research process, the researcher remained vigilant about potential biases, upholding objectivity and transparency. Ethical clearance was obtained from

relevant institutional review boards or ethics committees before initiating the study. The findings were reported truthfully and accurately, ensuring integrity. The potential benefits of the research for educational practices and policies were thoughtfully considered, aiming to contribute positively to the education system. Cultural sensitivity was observed, respecting local customs and practices, and the study prioritized inclusivity and diversity, encompassing a wide spectrum of centennial teachers and attitudes towards 21st-century learning. By adhering to these ethical considerations, the research was conducted responsibly and respectfully, prioritizing the rights and well-being of the participants and contributing valuable insights to the field of education within DepEd Sultan Kudarat.

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